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Participatory trail mapping for the promotion of proximity tourism

liminal shape rural futures

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1.1

Summary of the Action-Research¹

This report presents the results of the Reviving Trails action-research project, a participatory mapping initiative that took place in the summer of 2024. The main objective of the initiative was to develop and implement in Monti Prenestini a structured methodology for mapping, documenting, and digitally disseminating hiking trails. The motivation was to respond to the need to provide curated, well-described textual and photographic itineraries on the digital platforms most used by less experienced hikers, who are interested in grassroots tourism and often more likely to contribute to the local economy. The aim was thus to enhance local tourism offerings and, at the same time, to contribute to the preservation of the walkability of historic trails through more aware and informed traffic. The project sought to fill the significant gap in the digital presence of detailed itineraries for this territory (e.g., on platforms such as AllTrails), and structuring a scalable methodology that can be implemented in other areas.

During the Challenge, the team digitized, mapped and documented 7 different hikes totaling 41.5 km of trails, identifying and documenting 81 points of interest (POIs). The profiles were uploaded to 4 platforms – AllTrails, Komoot, Wikiloc and Outdooractive – for a total of 28 unique profiles, each tailored to the specific platform.

The program of activities included field mapping of routes with the highest tourism potential, creation of engaging narratives (storytelling), accurate documentation, and uploading of collected data. In addition, feasibility studies were conducted for further promotional activities, identifying 15 possible future initiatives and developing two Business Model Canvases² for proposals deemed to have the greatest potential impact.

The results of Reviving Trails represent a first step in demonstrating how targeted promotion of trails on navigation platforms can contribute to the creation of a local economy based on sustainable tourism. Trails made more digitally accessible improve the usability of natural and cultural heritage, facilitate safe hiking and create new opportunities for local economic activities. Documenting and enhancing hiking trails also contributes to the recognition of their value as a strategic asset for the local economy, indirectly incentivizing the maintenance of this vast heritage over time.

A framework was also developed during the project to assess the feasibility and impact of future initiatives to further bridge the digital divide. Using an impact-effort matrix, the project prioritized future actions to ensure optimal resource allocation and maximize community benefits. Finally, automated data

¹ Lewin, Kurt. "Action Research and Minority Problems." *Journal of Social Issues* 2 (1946): 34-46.

² Tool to visualize and briefly describe a business model.

management and analysis methodologies were developed to ensure the sustainability and replicability of these efforts on a larger scale.

2.1

Challenge Results

Fig. 1

Summary of achievements: kms of trails updated, itineraries and points of interest digitized and documented, promotion platforms and individual profiles uploaded.

Digitized and Documented Excursions		
41.5 km	Individual Hiking Itineraries	7
	Points of Interest	81
	Promotion Platforms	4
	Total Profiles Created	28

During the challenge, 7 different hikes totaling 41.5 km of trails were digitized, mapped, and documented, identifying and documenting 81 points of interest. Profiles were uploaded to 4 key platforms – AllTrails, Komoot, Wikiloc, and Outdooractive – generating 28 unique profiles, curated to fit the specifics of each platform and its audience. In parallel, feasibility studies were conducted that led to the identification of 15 potential future initiatives and the development of two detailed Business Model Canvases for the most promising proposals. These results provide a concrete basis for demonstrating how digital trail enhancement can stimulate a local and sustainable tourism economy.

Fig. 2

Photos illustrating the use of the page uploaded for the Punta dell'Olma itinerary in Rocca di Cave, available on AllTrails, for orientation on the trail.

2.2

Contextual Overview

The digitization of the Italian hiking network

Italy's hiking network, with more than 60,000 km of trails, represents one of the most extensive networks in Europe, a crucial infrastructure for land use and an integral part of local cultural heritage. These trails offer significant development opportunities for tourism, especially proximity tourism³, and serve as infrastructure for the well-being of residents. However, managing this vast network presents challenges: even the smallest or least resourced CAI (Italian Alpine Club) chapters often have to manage hundreds of kilometers, making maintenance and promotion operations complex.

Fig. 3

The user experience of the AllTrails App for navigating along the "Valle delle Cannucete" itinerary.

Increased and more conscious use of trails could help keep them cleaner and more walkable, complementing (but not replacing) active maintenance. By becoming attractions for tourism, especially proximity tourism, trails can create significant opportunities for the local economy, providing an additional incentive to maintain them over time. A preliminary analysis had shown that, at the time of the research, there was a paucity of curated and detailed trails in Monti Prenestini on the major hiking navigation apps (such as AllTrails, Komoot, etc). These platforms provide an ideal space for promotion, as they are the primary discovery and planning tool for less experienced hikers or

³ Tourism focused on exploring immediate national or regional destinations which are generally less known or frequented by the general public. Proximity tourism in the Italian context represents an important opportunity to reapproximate urban dwellers to their immediately surrounding rural context. The research team believes that it can play a crucial role in creating social and economic ties between urban and rural constituencies, particularly given growing interest in environmental issues and food systems.

those looking for ideas for a weekend daytrip; a target audience that is distinct from that of experienced hikers who perhaps already use platforms such as Waymarked Trails to download GPX tracks provided by CAI nationally.

In this context, Reviving Trails set out to develop and test a structured methodology to create, document, and disseminate curated trails precisely through these popular platforms, focusing on the qualitative and promotional aspects (descriptions, photos, points of interest) to attract new audiences. The goal was to provide a tool to promote local hiking experiences effectively, thus creating the digital infrastructure needed for proximity and sustainably-oriented tourism. Especially in areas where resources for digital promotion are limited, it is critical that there be a widespread presence of information on the platforms that visitors already rely on to navigate the territory. Through this approach, grounded in an analysis of the behavior of visitors that want to be reached, the impact of investments in territorial promotion can be maximized.

2.3

Methodological Approach

The mapping methodology developed followed an iterative process, characterized by a continuous back and forth between planning, fieldwork, data analysis and refinement.

Fig. 4

Example of a preparatory map for documentation of a hiking route, Attached to this report is the complete package including all maps made.

The work began with a preliminary discussion and field roundtable with the CAI section of Palestrina. This initial step was crucial to understand the state of the local trail network and to collaboratively identify an initial list of trails with

proximity tourism potential. From this comparison, we proceeded to select the routes to be mapped, trying to include at least two loop trails for each of the four main historic centers in the area (Castel San Pietro Romano, Capranica Prenestina, Rocca di Cave, Guadagnolo), in order to ensure homogeneous coverage and enhance the entire territory.

Preliminary research involved creating detailed base maps for each selected route, integrating all available geospatial information (existing tracks, contour lines, known points of interest) into a GIS database⁴. These maps, once printed, served both for orientation during outings and as a basis for noting new POIs⁵ and field observations.

Routes were designed starting from historic centers or easily accessible points (by car or public transport) and favoring routes of low or intermediate difficulty on CAI trails with signage considered to be in good condition – so as to ensure the safety of target users. This choice was in response to a twofold objective: to reach less experienced hikers and proximity tourists – targets with a greater propensity to contribute to the local economy – for whom the lack of curated digital information is a significant barrier in planning a weekend daytrip. In addition, loop routes close to the historic centers were assessed as capable of enriching their overall tourist experience, given they tend to have a limited number of POIs. With this in mind, routes were designed together with CAI looking beyond the naturalistic aspect. Attention was paid to creating a set of itineraries that included historical, geological and environmental assets, as well as traditional agricultural activities that persist in the territory and continue to shape its landscape.

During this preparatory phase, the working group divided into two teams:

1. **Geospatial Team:** Geospatial data collection, elevation profile processing, habitat analysis, base map preparation.
2. **Platform & Users Team:** Analyzing the functionality of target apps (AllTrails, Komoot, Wikiloc, Outdooractive), identifying best practices for content creation, and understanding different user profiles.

The field research week was characterized by an intense pace, alternating between mapping and documentation excursions during the morning and data processing and planning sessions in the afternoon/evening. The involvement of CAI volunteers from the local chapter was crucial in this phase.

The excursions took place with the group divided into two teams (4 researchers + 1 CAI volunteer per team). Within each team, roles were defined to optimize data collection:

1. **Navigator/CAI Interface:** Maintain contact with local CAI volunteers, translate directions, manage general routes.
2. **GPX tracker:** Record the precise GPS track of the route taken.
3. **POI Documenter:** Identify and document points of interest (natural, cultural, scenic, amenities) through a structured questionnaire with georeferencing capabilities.

⁴ Geographic Information System: A computer system for managing and analyzing geographic data.

⁵ Point of Interest.

4. **Photographer/Videomaker:** Take care of visual documentation of the trail, POIs, and landscapes, seeking a balance between seductive and useful images (e.g., documenting tricky spots, forks, or sections where it may be easy to miss the signage).

Fig. 5

The "Valle delle Cannuccete" itinerary uploaded to different platforms. From left to right: Komoot, AllTrails, Wikiloc, Outdooractive.

The morning hikes ranged in length from 2 to 4 hours. The afternoon after each hike was devoted to "cleaning," validating and processing the collected data (GPX tracks, POI notes). A key component of this phase was the creation of a detailed description sheet for each trail. This work included selecting and editing the photographic material collected during the morning and writing an effective narrative description (storytelling). The final sheet contained:

1. Refined GPX track.
2. Georeferenced and described list of POIs.
3. Technical information (length, elevation gain, estimated time, difficulty).
4. Accessibility information and potential critical issues.

The narrative description of the trail, designed to be engaging but also informative, highlighted the unique aspects of the hike and provided practical guidance (e.g., points where to pay attention).

These sheets served as the basis for creating the specific profiles for each of the 4 target platforms, adapting language and content to the different interfaces and types of users. The actual uploading of the profiles took place in the last days of the field phase and during the subsequent online phase.

In parallel and subsequent to the work on the trails, feasibility studies were conducted to assess the potential of 15 different future initiatives (related to promotion, maintenance, development of related services) and two detailed Business Model Canvases were developed for the ideas deemed most promising in terms of impact and sustainability.

2.4

Challenges and Limitations

Despite the positive results achieved, the Reviving Trails project allowed some inherent challenges and limitations to surface. First, the impact of weather conditions proved critical, the weight of which had been underestimated in the planning phase. Indeed, field activities were severely constrained by bad weather, which limited useful windows for hiking and documentation, requiring considerable organizational flexibility. This led, in some cases, to the abandonment of certain stretches. This is a critical factor for the replicability and scalability of similar methodologies in tight time frames.

Another significant challenge emerged in managing promotional output. Since this was mainly qualitative (photographs, narrative texts) and geared toward a general audience – as a complement to the technical information already provided by CAI – there was a difficulty in achieving homogeneous results of predictable quality by working with different teams. Different individual skills and sensibilities in areas such as photography, creative writing (storytelling), and the ability to capture the most attractive elements of a trail inevitably influenced the final product. Ensuring a consistently high standard of quality therefore requires specific training and more detailed guidelines.

In addition, several technical and functional limitations related to the navigation platforms used to disseminate the profiles emerged. In particular, the difficulty, or sometimes inability, to easily update published profiles to reflect real changes on the trail (such as new signage, landslides, or closures) was noted. This is compounded by the lack of a clear hierarchy between "official" or verified trails and those uploaded spontaneously by users in some platforms, which can lead to user confusion.

Finally, it was necessary to reconsider the initial assumption that increased use could directly contribute to trail maintenance. Field experience showed that although increased circulation can help keep the walking surface clean, this does not replace the need for active and constant maintenance, especially for weed control (very aggressive in the Apennine climate) and repair of structural damage.

However, it is important to point out that digital promotion aimed at a general audience, by attracting interested and potentially more spending-prone proximity tourists to the area, can generate economic spin-offs and increase the perceived value of trails. This recognition of their potential as tourist attractors can, in turn, act as a strong incentive for local communities, governments, and economic operators to invest in or support more of the necessary maintenance activities, seeing them as a strategic investment rather than an unjustifiable cost. Consequently, digital promotion and maintenance should be seen as complementary and interdependent strategies.

2.5

Conclusions

The Reviving Trails project successfully demonstrated that a structured methodology for mapping, documenting, and digitally disseminating hiking trails is feasible and can produce significant results in a relatively short period of time. The targeted digitization and promotion of 7 itineraries (41.5 km) and 81 points of interest on 4 key platforms has laid the foundation for increasing the accessibility and attractiveness of the trail network of Monti Prenestini, specifically targeting less experienced hikers and proximity tourists.

The approach confirmed the potential of digital enhancement to stimulate the local economy related to sustainable tourism, making it easier to safely discover and enjoy the opportunities offered by the territory. However, the project also highlighted important limitations and challenges. The strong (and initially underestimated) dependence on weather conditions, the difficulty in ensuring consistent quality of promotional content produced, and the functional limitations of current digital platforms. Fundamentally, it emerged that digital promotion, while crucial, cannot be divorced from a concrete and ongoing commitment to physical trail maintenance. An increase in use does not in itself guarantee walkability, which requires constant and organized interventions.

Reviving Trails offers a valid and replicable methodological model, but emphasizes the need for an integrated approach. In order to turn potentials into lasting benefits for the territory, it is first essential to integrate digital promotion with investments in maintenance, and figure out an expedient way of developing homogenous skills in the creation of high-quality content by initiative participants.

3.1

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